

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TERRITORIES OF UKRAINE UNDER CURRENT CONDITIONS

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Abstract. The theoretical and methodological principles of state management of territorial development are substantiated. The scientific understanding of territorial development as a complex process aimed not only at economic growth, but also at ensuring the functional balance, viability, and long-term capacity of territories in an unstable environment is clarified. The theoretical provisions of ensuring the stability, adaptability, and security of territories as a methodological basis of modern state regional policy are substantiated. It is proved that the mentioned categories are not isolated characteristics of territorial development, but form a single conceptual framework within which the territory appears as a system capable of maintaining critical functions, counteracting external shocks, adapting to new conditions and moving towards restoration and modernization. The current state of regulatory, institutional and organizational support for state management of territorial development in Ukraine is analyzed, which made it possible to identify key structural imbalances and functional limitations of the current system. It was found that, despite the updating of the legislative framework, the development of decentralization, the expansion of the powers of territorial communities and the introduction of strategic planning, the territorial development management system continues to be characterized by uneven community capacity, insufficient coordination between levels of public authority, weak integration of strategic and budgetary decisions and limited readiness to function in conditions of external threats. A comprehensive assessment of the impact of external challenges and threats on the development of the territories of Ukraine was carried out, which allowed us to establish their multidimensional, systemic, and spatially differentiated nature. It is shown that military, demographic, economic, humanitarian, environmental and security factors not only increase interregional disparities, but also change the functional load of individual communities and regions, transform the structure of local economies, deepen infrastructural vulnerability and reduce the level of financial and institutional stability. The priorities for improving the mechanisms of state management of territorial development in Ukraine have been substantiated and scientific and practical recommendations for their implementation in the regulatory, institutional, strategic, financial and economic, digital, security and partnership dimensions have been developed. It has been proven that only a comprehensive combination of these areas creates the appropriate prerequisites for the formation of an adaptive, sustainable, security-oriented and effective system of state management of territorial development.

Keywords: public administration, regional policy, region, territorial security, external challenges, decentralization, strategic planning.

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Introduction.

The current stage of Ukraine's development is characterized by profound transformations of the public administration system, a rethinking of the role of the state in ensuring the stability of territories, as well as the growing influence of external challenges and threats on the socio-economic, demographic, infrastructural and security dynamics of regions and territorial communities. Under these conditions, territorial development ceases to be only a matter of spatial organization of the economy or a tool for reducing interregional disparities. It acquires strategic importance as a component of national security, territorial stability, social cohesion and state capacity to ensure the viability of regions and communities in conditions of instability. The relevance of the topic is enhanced by the fact that the full-scale war led to a qualitative change in the conditions of functioning of the territories of Ukraine. Some of them suffered direct destruction, some faced significant demographic, social and infrastructural overload, while others faced the need for rapid adaptation to new economic, security and logistical conditions. As a result, traditional mechanisms of state management of territorial development have proven to be insufficiently flexible to effectively respond to modern challenges. This necessitates their scientific rethinking and the development of new approaches focused on adaptability, multi-level coordination, typologically differentiated support for territories, combining development with restoration, and including a security component in the system of state regional policy.

The theoretical basis of the study was the scientific works of domestic scientists, which revealed theoretical and methodological, institutional, organizational, financial and economic, security, and digital aspects of state management of territorial development. A significant contribution to the formation of theoretical foundations of territorial development and regional policy was made by Z. Gerasymchuk [3], A. Buryachenko [1], V. Kuybida [5], N. Liba [7], Z. Buryk [8], M. Vyshyvanyuk [2], Ya. Zhovnirchik [4], and A. Lelechenko [6].

A review of the above scientific works gives grounds to assert that the issues of adaptive management of territories in conditions of military and post-war instability, a typologically differentiated approach to territories, integration of the security dimension into state regional policy, as well as institutional and digital support for development and recovery processes remain insufficiently developed. It is this scientific gap that determines the relevance of the research topic.

The purpose of the article is scientific substantiation of theoretical and conceptual provisions, institutional and organizational mechanisms and practical directions for improving public administration of the development of territories of Ukraine in the face of external challenges and threats.

Results.

It has been established that the evolution of scientific approaches to public management of territorial development reflects the transformation of the management paradigm itself [3; 5; 4; 2; 7; 6; 8]: from an administratively centralized vision of the territory as an object of power influence to a modern understanding of it as a complex, open, multifunctional, and dynamic system. It has been determined that within the framework of classical approaches, priority was given to hierarchy, regulatory regulation, state control, and resource redistribution, while modern concepts focus on strategic planning, multi-level governance, decentralization, institutional capacity, partnership, digitalization, and security-oriented development.

It is substantiated that the concepts of "state administration", "territory", "region", "territorial development" and "state administration of territorial development" should not be considered in isolation, but as an interconnected system of scientific categories that reflects the object, subject, content, functional purpose and instrumental support of state influence on spatial processes. On this basis, it is proven that state administration of territorial

development should be defined as a purposeful, systematically organized, normatively regulated, and multi-level activity of state authorities, local governments, and other subjects of public governance. This activity is aimed at the formation and implementation of mechanisms for ensuring balanced, sustainable, adaptive and safe development of territories, taking into account their potential, disparities, risks and restoration needs.

The essential and functional characteristics of the mechanisms of state management of territorial development in crisis situations are revealed. It is proven that these mechanisms have a multicomponent and multifunctional nature, and their content consists of a combination of legal, institutional, organizational, economic, strategic, information-analytical and security means of influence. With the help of which the regulation, coordination, stabilization, adaptation, restoration and further transformation of territorial systems are ensured. The mechanisms of state management of territorial development are classified by the nature of managerial influence, level of implementation, time orientation, method of influence, degree of universality and dominant result.

Special attention is paid to the justification of the principles of formation and implementation of state management mechanisms of territorial development. It has been established that, along with the classical principles of legality, systematicity, strategic orientation and efficiency, in the conditions of external challenges and threats, the principles of subsidiarity, multi-level governance, coordination and partnership, adaptability, sustainability, security orientation, resource balance, transparency, participation and innovation acquire leading importance. It is this system of principles that ensures the formation of a model of public administration, which is at the same time normatively ordered, strategically oriented, flexible to environmental changes and capable of supporting territories in the modes of prevention, response, stabilization and restoration. In this way, the principles of public administration of territorial development are revealed not only as general normative guidelines, but as a functional basis for building a modern adaptive system of territorial policy.

It is proven that the stability of territories reflects their integral ability to maintain functionality, manageability and potential for recovery under the influence of destabilizing factors; adaptability characterizes the ability of territorial systems and their management mechanisms to change internal modes of functioning, tools and priorities in accordance with new conditions; the security of territories determines the degree of protection of the population, infrastructure, institutions and resource potential from threats that can disrupt the viability of the territory or destroy the prospects for its development. It is argued that only in combination these categories create an opportunity to form a modern theoretical model of territorial policy, in which development is considered not only as growth, but as a protected, sustainable, flexible and restorative functioning of the territorial system. In this regard, a conceptual system for ensuring the stability, adaptability and security of territories has been formed, which includes target, subject, functional, resource and effective blocks that interact within a single management cycle. It is substantiated that its functioning should take place in preventive, reactive-stabilization and restoration-transformation modes, which allows not only to respond to the crisis, but also to form the prerequisites for the structural renewal of territories. It is proven that territorial development in Ukraine is implemented within the framework of a complex multi-level system of public administration, which includes the constitutional principles of territorial organization, special legislation in the field of state regional policy, regulatory support for strategic planning, legal mechanisms of decentralization, as well as an extensive institutional architecture of state authorities, local governments, regional development agencies and other structures involved in the processes of development and restoration of territories. It has been determined that it is the existing regulatory and institutional system that forms the basic environment for the implementation of state regional policy, however, its current state demonstrates the presence of not only

significant results of modernization, but also a number of internal limitations that hinder the achievement of balanced, sustainable and security-oriented territorial development.

It has been established that in recent years the legal field of territorial development in Ukraine has undergone a qualitative update: along with the classical tasks of regional equalization and supporting the capacity of communities, the tasks of restoration, reconstruction, security and stability of territories have been integrated into it, which indicates a gradual transition to a new model of state regional policy, oriented not only towards development, but also towards the restorative transformation of space. It has been found that, despite significant achievements in decentralization, the practice of implementing territorial policy is still characterized by uneven institutional capacity of communities and regions, different levels of quality of management decisions, blurring of individual functional boundaries and the preservation of elements of sectoral isolation in the management of territorial development. It is especially important that in the conditions of war, these problems underwent a qualitative transformation: they ceased to be only a manifestation of the institutional incompleteness of reforms and turned into factors that directly affect the ability of territories to maintain viability, respond to threats, provide basic services, coordinate recovery processes, and maintain administrative continuity. This gave grounds to conclude that modern state regional policy requires not only the improvement of individual procedures or tools, but also a deeper renewal of the organizational and managerial model of its implementation on the principles of multi-level governance, clear functional demarcation, adaptability, strategic coherence, and digital support for administrative decisions.

It is proven that armed aggression, demographic crisis, economic instability, environmental risks and humanitarian and security challenges simultaneously affect the economic base of territories, the state of infrastructure, human potential, financial capacity of communities, the level of institutional capacity and the possibility of further recovery. It is established that the most significant consequence of external threats was not only a decrease in general development parameters, but also a deep deformation of the spatial structure of the country, which is manifested in uneven losses, demographic redistribution of the population, increased territorial asymmetry, changes in the economic functions of individual regions and the emergence of new types of vulnerable territories. In this regard, it is substantiated that the development of the territories of Ukraine in modern conditions should be assessed not only through traditional indicators of economic growth or budgetary capacity, but primarily through the categories of sustainability, adaptability, security, functional integrity and recovery capacity. It is determined that further improvement of the mechanisms of state management of the development of the territories of Ukraine should be based on a differentiated approach to different types of territories, integration of security and restoration components into regional policy, strengthening the institutional capacity of communities and regions, as well as on the transition to a model of public administration that combines development, stabilization, reconstruction and long-term spatial modernization into a single system of state influence.

A scientific and methodological approach to a comprehensive assessment of the impact of external threats on the development of the territories of Ukraine is proposed, the essence of which is to consider armed aggression, demographic crisis, economic instability, environmental risks and humanitarian and security challenges not as separate destabilizing factors, but as an interconnected complex of spatial transformations that simultaneously affect the economic base of the territories, the state of infrastructure, human potential, financial capacity of communities and the institutional capacity of the regions. Unlike existing approaches, which mostly focus on individual sectoral or socio-economic parameters, the proposed approach provides a multidimensional assessment of territorial development, taking into account the spatial asymmetry of losses, the level of vulnerability of territories, their adaptability and recovery potential. This made it possible to justify the need to

transition to a differentiated, security-oriented and recovery-oriented model of state management of territorial development, within which the managerial impact is determined taking into account the actual state of territorial systems, the scale of their structural deformations and the prospects for further stabilization and modernization.

A conceptual model of adaptive management of the development of territories of Ukraine has been developed, which is considered as a holistic system of public influence aimed at ensuring sustainable, safe, differentiated and restoration-oriented development of territories in the face of external challenges and threats. Its content consists in a combination of systemic, strategic, security, sustainability, restoration and multi-level approaches, which together form a new logic of state regional policy. Unlike traditional management models, focused mainly on a stable environment, the key in the proposed model is the constant adjustment of strategies, mechanisms, tools and regimes of management influence depending on changes in the external environment, security situation, scale of destruction, level of territorial vulnerability and restoration capacity of communities and regions. The model includes interconnected target, subject, analytical and diagnostic, functional and mechanism, resource, digital monitoring and performance blocks that ensure the integrity of adaptive governance. It is focused on the transition from a universal model of regional policy to a system of public administration in which the managerial influence is determined taking into account the type of territory, the level of its security vulnerability, the scale of infrastructure losses, resource potential and prospects for structural modernization.

The directions of adaptation of international experience are justified through the selective use of those foreign practices that are functionally suitable for Ukrainian conditions and meet the modern needs of territorial development and recovery. It has been established that the most relevant for Ukraine are European approaches to multi-level governance, decentralization, asymmetric managerial influence, smart specialization, digital monitoring and reconstruction through modernization. In this context, the priority areas of adaptation are: strengthening strategic coordination between the state, regional and local levels; introducing typologically differentiated support for territories depending on the level of vulnerability and recovery potential; using smart specialization tools to form new points of economic growth; integrating digital monitoring platforms into the management decision-making system; and applying the principle of “reconstruction through modernization”, according to which the restoration of territories is considered not as a simple reproduction of the pre-war state, but as an opportunity to update their spatial, infrastructural and economic structure. It is substantiated that the adaptation of international experience should be carried out not by mechanically copying external models, but through their institutional, organizational and resource coordination with Ukrainian realities, the scale of external threats, the uneven capacity of territories and the needs of post-war restoration.

Proposals for improving the mechanisms of state management of the development of territories of Ukraine cover a complex of interrelated areas that form the applied basis for the modernization of state regional policy. First of all, a regulatory and legal update of management mechanisms is proposed by enshrining in the legislation the categories of adaptability, resilience, territorial vulnerability, recovery capacity and security and resilience profile of the territory, as well as the introduction of a typologically differentiated approach to state support. In the institutional dimension, the feasibility of strengthening the role of the regional level as a link of strategic coordination, functional expansion of the capabilities of regional development agencies, the development of regional platforms for coordination of development and recovery and the creation of mechanisms for institutional support of weaker communities is substantiated. In the strategic dimension, a transition to scenario-based, adaptive, security-oriented and resource-based strategizing, integrated with the budget process and digital monitoring, is proposed. In the financial and economic sphere, the need to improve inter-budgetary relations, develop financial equalization mechanisms, form

specialized funds for adaptive territorial development, support the internal financial potential of communities and stimulate investment activity has been proven. In the digital dimension, the creation of a single digital platform for territorial development management, the introduction of digital community profiles, integrated monitoring systems, geoanalytical tools, early warning mechanisms for risks and evidence-based management standards have been proposed. Separately, the need to integrate the security and sustainability dimension into public administration mechanisms has been substantiated, as well as the development of partnership and inter-municipal mechanisms that should ensure the expansion of the resource base for development, the improvement of the quality of public services, the strengthening of horizontal cooperation and the reduction of institutional weaknesses of individual territories have been substantiated. The totality of these proposals forms a holistic applied concept for improving public administration for the development of territories of Ukraine in the face of external challenges and threats.

Conclusion.

The theoretical and methodological provisions of state management of territorial development are specified. It is substantiated that state management of territorial development should be considered as a complex multi-level system of public influence, combining spatial, socio-economic, institutional, organizational and security dimensions. This allowed us to deepen the scientific understanding of territorial development as a complex process aimed not only at economic growth, but also at ensuring the functional balance, viability and long-term capacity of territories in an unstable environment. The theoretical and conceptual provisions of stability, adaptability and security of territories as a methodological basis of modern state regional policy are substantiated. It is proved that the specified categories are not isolated characteristics of territorial development, but form a single conceptual framework within which the territory appears as a system capable of maintaining critical functions, counteracting external shocks, adapting to new conditions, and moving towards restoration and modernization. This approach made it possible to rethink the priorities of public administration, shifting them from mainly compensatory solutions to mechanisms of prevention, increasing resilience and forming institutional readiness of territories to long-term challenges and threats.

The current state of regulatory, institutional and organizational support for public administration of territorial development in Ukraine was analyzed, which made it possible to identify key structural imbalances and functional limitations of the current system. It was found that, despite the updating of the legislative framework, the development of decentralization, the expansion of the powers of territorial communities, and the introduction of strategic planning, the territorial development management system continues to be characterized by uneven capacity of communities, insufficient coordination between levels of public authority, weak integration of strategic and budgetary decisions and limited readiness to function in conditions of external threats. This gives grounds to argue that further improvement of state regional policy should be carried out in the direction of systemic institutional modernization, and not only point-by-point adjustment of its individual elements.

It's based conceptual model of adaptive management of the development of territories of Ukraine has been developed, built on the principles of multi-level coordination, typologically differentiated approach, digital monitoring, resource balance and regenerative capacity of territories. Its structure, which includes target, subject, analytical and diagnostic, functional and mechanism, resource, digital and effective blocks, the interaction of which ensures the integrity of managerial influence, has been substantiated. The proposed model creates a methodological and applied basis for the integration of development, security, stabilization,

restoration and modernization into a single system of public administration that meets the modern needs of territorial development of Ukraine in conditions of prolonged instability.

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